

Klimaxo

Developed by: Volker Kast

Article contributed by: Volker Kast

Keywords

Business, Climate-change Education, Climate Policy Education, Consumer Psychology, Ecology, Economics, Environmental Law, Nature Conservation, Political Science, Renewable Energies, Risk Management, Sustainability, Systems Thinking

Figure 1. Photograph of the game *Klimaxo* showing the box and components. Image used for educational review; rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The importance of climate change as a global challenge no longer needs to be highlighted. Atmospheric CO₂ ppm levels continue to rise, and the consequences are becoming increasingly evident. At the same time, the proportion of environmentally conscious people is also increasing. However, the topic is complex, and it is often unclear how to implement climate protection effectively.

This is where *Klimaxo* (see Figure 1) comes in. *Klimaxo* is a scientifically grounded strategy game that makes complex climate knowledge tangible through innovative game mechanics.

As an analogue card game, its rules can be learned in ten minutes using the online explainer video.

The central goal of Klimaxo is to enable constructive dialogue about climate protection and to convey practical action-oriented knowledge. The core focus lies on estimating the magnitudes of CO₂ emissions generated individually or collectively. The game translates complex climate relationships into easy-to-remember rules of thumb, reducing the feeling of being overwhelmed. Through strategy, knowledge, and luck, dynamic rounds emerge that work across various knowledge levels. The game was developed by Volker Kast (education expert) in collaboration with Martin Merten (environmental psychologist).

Facts

Release date:	May 2024
Developer:	Volker Kast
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	2–6; with more than six players, playing in teams of two is possible
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	Minimum 30–40 minutes including the desired debates; optimal duration: 1–1.5 hours
Languages:	German
Environment:	Play surface and seating
Material:	Online explainer video for a quick start: https://www.klimaxo.de/pages/anleitung . Starting with the classic printed rulebook is more time-consuming, but it is possible.
Price:	24.50 euros per game (2025). Universities may receive funding for this (e.g., through Engagement Global).

Resonance & Criticism

Klimaxo has already gained wide recognition within the sustainability community. The concept was awarded at the Impact Slam Hamburg 2023 for its climate-protection potential. Its nomination for the German Award for Sustainability Projects 2025 further highlights the positive reception.

Players particularly emphasise the well-balanced mix between knowledge transfer and enjoyable gameplay. The game convinces with its clear presentation of complex relationships and real-life relevance. Participants are encouraged to engage in scientifically grounded debates in a relaxed atmosphere, without moralising. Experts especially appreciate the high professional quality ensured by integrating current climate research.

Game principle & Process

Klimaxo is a strategic analogue card game that simulates global warming on a board ranging from 0 to 3 degrees. At the beginning, players are randomly assigned roles pursuing different interests regarding global warming. This makes antagonistic positions possible and leads to engaging perspective shifts.

In several rounds, the game piece “Earth” is moved on the temperature scale through various actions. If players succeed in manoeuvring Earth into the temperature range associated with their role, they score points. Whoever has the most points after all rounds wins. The Earth’s temperature is influenced by action cards featuring realistic “climate actions” with scientifically grounded CO₂ values. Event cards add societal random events.

Between rounds, players can win jokers through a CO₂-estimation mini-game. This mechanic is central to the learning process: While players initially struggle to estimate CO₂ magnitudes, they develop a more accurate sense over time. Built-in balancing mechanisms for experienced players ensure a level playing field.

The combination of educational content and competitive elements makes Klimaxo particularly dynamic. Competition and estimation questions foster both social interaction and topic-related discussion.

Ouariachi et al. (2020) identify the following elements as crucial for achieving strong learning effects and behaviour change through games: The available actions must be within reach, the challenge must be sufficiently difficult, trust in provided information must exist, performance evaluation must be possible, and the game should evoke strong emotions through meaningful relevance.

Learning objectives & Educational fields of application

The game’s primary goal is to help players better assess CO₂ emissions and their magnitudes. It highlights aspects in which society systematically misjudges climate impact. For example, the influence of private plastic consumption is generally greatly overestimated, whereas emissions from all cow-related products are often underestimated.

Climate change is overwhelming for many people when navigating daily decisions. Klimaxo counters this overload with simple rules of thumb, such as: seasonal food generally has a significantly more positive climate effect than regionality alone. In the game, players estimate CO₂ emissions to gain strategic advantages. At the same time, these rules of thumb are read aloud as “tips”. The resulting discussions, grounded in scientific data, aim to generate memorable insights or spark deeper engagement with the topic. An instructor can moderate the debates, deepen the questions, ask for takeaways at the end, or join the game themselves.

Klimaxo is well-suited for university courses, sustainability workshops, or team-building events. It can also be used in schools, provided an appropriate time slot (1–1.5 hours) and a focused and sustainability-interested class are available. As a serious game, Klimaxo addresses

people with a basic interest in sustainability—from students to sustainability managers to families. Universities, climate clubs, and sustainability-focused companies use it successfully in climate education.

The scientific basis of the game was validated by environmental psychologists at the University of Magdeburg. The data and scenarios are based on current research and are expected to remain valid until at least 2035—barring unexpected developments.

Effectiveness

So far (2025), evidence is limited to anecdotally documented experiences collected through user surveys. Common reactions include surprise and self-reflection, with comments such as “I never would have guessed that”, “Ah, I’m actually doing pretty well here”, or similar remarks. Statements such as “We all know so little” from sustainability managers illustrate the game’s high potential for knowledge gain.

Laughter about the assigned in-game roles, competitive remarks, and factual discussions are also consistently observed. Players often express motivation to share content with others, saying things like “I should really tell my boss about this” or “I definitely want to play this with my kids.”

Comments such as “Oh, so installing solar panels has that much impact? Then let’s do it—we’ve been thinking about it for a long time” indicate strengthened climate-protective impulses, and similar reactions occur across many topic areas. A flow state is often observed as players become fully immersed in the game and engage in lively discussions for one to two hours.

Potentially problematic aspects

Klimaxo consistently uses gender-inclusive language and ensures diverse representation in its game characters. The effects of anthropogenic climate change are supported by a strong scientific consensus. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) regularly publishes internationally recognised reports. Despite clear evidence, some people doubt human-caused climate change. Frondel et al. (2021) find that the share of climate sceptics in Germany in 2020 was approximately 9%. For these individuals, the game may be less suitable. However, players report that Klimaxo can still facilitate relaxed climate discussions even with sceptical friends.

Reviewer(s): Sigfried Zürn, Martin Gerner

Sources

- Ouariachi, T., Li, C.-Y., & Elving, W. J. L. (2020). Gamification approaches for education and engagement on pro-environmental behaviors: Searching for best practices. *Sustainability*, *12*(11), 4565. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114565>
- Frondel, M., Kükenenthal, V. C., Larysch, T., & Osberghaus, D. (2021). *Wahrnehmung des Klimawandels in Deutschland: Eine Längsschnittbefragung privater Haushalte* (RWI Materialien No. 142). RWI – Leibniz-Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung. <https://hdl.handle.net/10419/251875>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (n.d.). *IPCC*. Retrieved December 31, 2025, from <https://www.ipcc.ch/>